

STYLISTIC DEVICES AND THEIR TYPES IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

Achilov Oybek Rustamovich¹, Olimjonova Fazilat Rustam qizi²

¹Associate Professor of Tashkent state transport university, ²Tashkent State Transport University
Student of TNI-3r-24 group

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Annotation. This article examines stylistic devices and the types of them in English literature. Stylistic devices play essential role in enriching literary texts, giving them emotional depth, expressiveness, and individual style. The study discusses various types of stylistic devices, such as metaphors, simile, personification and others, illustrating their functions through examples from classical and modern English literature.

Key words: stylistic devices, literary text, style in texts, linguistic adaptation, cultural context, narrative voice, figurative language.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена изучению стилистических приемов и их видов в английской литературе. Стилистические приемы играют важную роль в обогащении литературных текстов, придавая им эмоциональную глубину, выразительность и индивидуальный стиль. В исследовании рассматриваются различные виды стилистических приемов такие как метафора, сравнение, персонификация и другие. Также с примерами из классической и современной английской литературы. Особое внимание уделено значению этих приемов в передаче художественного замысла автора и созданию яркого впечатления у читателя.

Ключевые слова: стилистические приемы, художественный текст, стили в тексте, языковая адаптация, культурный контекст, повествовательный голос, образовательный язык.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola adabiyotdagi stilistik vositalar va ularning turlarining o`rganishga bag`ishlangan. Stilistik vositalar adabiy matnlarni boyitishda, ularga hissiy chuqurlik, ifodaviylik va individual uslub berishda muhim rol o`ynaydi tadqiqotda metafora, taqqoslash, personifikatsiya va boshqalar ko`rib chiqilib, klassik va zamonaviy ingliz adabiyotidan misollar keltiriladi. Ushbu vositalarning muallifning badiiy niyatini yetkazish va o`quvchida yorqin taassurot qoldirishdagi ahamiyatiga alohida e`tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so`zlar: uslubiy vositalar, badiiy asar, matndagi uslublari, lingvistik moslashuv, madaniy kontekst, hikoya ohangi, obraz tili.

Introduction. A literary text belongs to the field of artistic literature. In such a text, the author enjoys full creative freedom to express ideas in any form they choose, often using a special style and figurative language to give the work a distinct poetic quality. To fully analyze and understand a literary text, it is essential to grasp its nature and key elements. Each of these components answers fundamental questions such as who, what, where, when, why and how. Without them, the narrative loses coherence and becomes difficult to comprehend.

The main elements of a literary text include: Plot- the sequence of events and character actions that form the foundation of the narrative. Narrator- the voice or entity through which the story is told; it may be a person, an animal, or an omniscient observer. Point of view- the perspective from which the story is conveyed. Theme- the central idea, message, or subject

explored by the author. Characters- the individuals or beings who drive the action forward. Setting- the time, place, and context in which the events unfold. Language- the tone and style the author adopts to express their message. Conflict- the central tension or struggle that provides motivation and direction to the story. Overall, literary texts aim to evoke emotional responses, create vivid imagery, and reflect the author's unique voice. They frequently employ figurative language, stylistic devices, and cultural references to engage readers and convey meanings that go beyond the literal meaning. In summary, literary texts are creative works that reflect the author's imagination, emotions and unique voice. Through the use of vivid imagery, figurative language, and stylistic devices literary texts invite readers to explore deeper meanings beyond the surface of the narrative [1,2].

Since stylistic devices add color, enrich the meaning, and even deeply explain the essence of a work, understanding and studying them is a crucial task. Through the studying these devices, the reader will begin to understand the text much more deeply than before, and the essence of each idea from the author will appear even more interesting. Over time, the reader themselves will start to recognize these devices. Understanding stylistic devices is also important for translators, as it allows them to perfectly and accurately convey the author's message in their work. For stylistic devices we can count: metaphor, adnomination, allegory, alliteration, allusion, anaphora, antithesis, apostrophe, assonance and consonance, cataphora, climax and anticlimax, charactonym, ellipsis, euphemism, epigram, hyperbole, hypophora, irony, merism, metalipsis, metonymy, onomatopoeia, oxymoron, parallelism, parenthesis, personification, pun, rhetorical question, simile, synecdoche, tautology, zeugma. When they are all are sometimes used in the literature, only some of them are often used and they can be found in all literary works: metaphor, simile, personification, and alliteration[3,4].

Metaphor. A metaphor is a figure of speech where one thing is compared to something else, two seemingly unrelated things to show a deeper meaning. To put it simply, it says something *is* something else. This makes language more creative and allows the writer to explain complex ideas in a way that is easier to understand or more emotional. There are also types of metaphor: implied metaphor- this suggests comparison without directly saying it; visual metaphor- this uses images to show a comparison rather than stating it; extended metaphor- this is a metaphor that continues over several lines or paragraphs; dead metaphor- these are metaphors that have been used so much they have lost their original impact and have become clichés. Example and analysis: from Toni Morrison's poem, *Eve Remembering*: I bit power to the core. Is a metaphor that symbolizes not just struggling with power, but trying to get to its very essence. It is likely the person is not only resisting the outward power but is attempting to understand its foundation, what lies behind this control. This expression reflects the character's desire to overcome the psychological and emotional scars left by slavery. They are trying not just to survive, but to destroy the power that has controlled their lives for so long, delving into deepest and most painful aspects[5,6].

Simile. Is a device that draws comparisons between two different things to highlight their similarities, using words like or as. It is a way to bring imagery to life and create a deeper understanding of a subject. Similes have a unique power in that they can evoke emotion or provoke thought by emphasizing a certain characteristic of an object or person, turning idea or feeling into something easier to visualize. The main difference from metaphor is: a metaphor says something *is* something, while a simile says something *like* something. Example and analysis: I wandered lonely as a cloud. By William Wordsworth. Wordsworth uses a simile- he compares himself to a lonely cloud with the word as. The cloud drifts freely across the sky, and

similarly, the poet feels a sense of detachment from the world, peace, and solitude- but not in a painful way[7,8]. .

Personification. Is when you give human traits to something nonhuman. Personification is used to make our writing more relatable to the reader, to help bring more clarity to the ideas or illustrate an environment. Epresentation of something abstract and unreal. It is mostly used in fairytales because of their magic tools to take reader`s attention and help them feel it deeply. Example and analysis: Wilderness swallows you up. From Amy Clampitt`s poem The sun underfoot among the sundews. This personification creates a feeling that the wilderness is not passive, it is active, overwhelming, and even devouring. It suggests that when you enter the wilderness, you do not just walk, you are consumed by it, lost in it, overpowered. Wilderness is personified to make the reader feel overwhelmed by the natural world, as if wilderness is a monster with jawsto swallow you whole[9].

Alliteration. Is a device where the same consonant sound is repeated at the start of nearby words. We can find this rhythmical sentences in poetry, prose and also songs. When we start to think how it uses how it functions we have to understand that this si not about repeating the same latter for many times but repeating the same sound. As purposes of using we can say: add rhythym- it makes reading or listening more musical and pleaent; emphasize words-it makes some words stand out more; create mood-repeated sounds can bring out emotions- harsh sounds feel dark, soft sounds feel calm; make things memorable- alliteration makes lines catchier and easier to remember. Example and analysis: The silver sea sparkled, sending shimmering signals to the shore. From Harry potter and Scorcerer`s stone by J.K. Rowling. The soft s sound creates a smooth, flowing, almost magical atmosphere it mimics the sound of the sea itself, gentle and soothing. Rowling uses this alliteration to make the scene feel more vivid and alive , pulling th reader deeper into the sensory beauty of the moment.

Conclusion. In conclusion, stylistic devices play a crucial role in enriching English literary texts, allowing authors to convey emotions, emphasize ideas, and engage readers on deeper levels. From vivid imagery created through personification and metaphor to the rhythmic effects of alliteration and repetition, each device contributes to the unique voice. By analyzing various types of stylistic devices, readers can gain valuable tools for interpreting texts.

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